



Vector backbone: pBluescript KS

PmH4p, *P. multistriata* H4 gene promoter; GFP, green fluorescent protein; MRP2, Mating-type Related Plus 2 gene coding sequence; Gene ID: 0122240 (Russo et al., 2018); PtLhcf1t, *P. tricornutum* Lhcf1 gene terminator.

This plasmid is suitable for *P. multistriata* biolistic transformation and is used to overexpress and tag the MRP2 gene.